

ACCURATE ESTIMATION OF THE ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF POROUS FIBERS

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SUMMARY: A procedure is described to calculate polycrystalline anisotropic fiber elastic properties with cylindrical symmetry and porosity. It uses a preferred orientation model (tomé ellipsoidal self-consistent model) for the determination of anisotropic elastic properties for the case of highly oriented carbon fibers. The model predictions, corrected for porosity, are compared to back-calculated fiber elastic properties of an IM6/3501-6 unidirectional composite whose elastic properties have been determined via resonant ultrasound spectroscopy. The Halpin-Tsai equations used to back-calculated fiber elastic properties are found to be inappropriate for anisotropic composite constituents. Modifications are proposed to the Halpin-Tsai equations to expand their applicability to anisotropic reinforcement materials.

KEYWORDS: anisotropy, elastic properties, preferred orientation, porosity correction, resonant ultrasound spectroscopy, self-consistent methods.

INTRODUCTION

Many reinforcement materials commonly used in composites are anisotropic and polycrystalline with a strong preferred orientation. A long standing and difficult problem is the estimation of the anisotropic constituent elastic properties because experimental measurements of non-axial reinforcement properties are often difficult. Numerical methods for simulating bulk composite material performance require composite constituent elastic properties and would benefit from accurate estimates of constituent anisotropic elastic properties.

The Halpin-Tsai equations accurately describe composite elastic properties when the constituent materials are isotropic [1]. Application of the Halpin-Tsai equations to composites consisting of anisotropic constituent materials, such as carbon and graphite fibers, require accurate determination of the constituent elastic properties. The longitudinal fiber properties are relatively easy to measure, but measurement of the transverse and shear properties are very difficult.

Graphite is one of the most anisotropic single crystals currently known. The single crystal anisotropy arises due to the bonding types within the lattice. Figure 1 shows the lattice of graphite and its two different bond types. Sp^2 bonds are strong planar bonds, while π^* bonds are weak. Table 1 lists unirradiated and irradiated graphite single crystal elastic constants.

Blakslee et. al. [2] values were measured from highly oriented compression annealed pyrolytic polycrystalline graphite which can be made in dimensions large enough for accurate determination of elastic properties via standard testing techniques. Naturally occurring graphite single crystals are often only a few millimeters in size which limits the testing methods applicable for determining elastic constants [2]. Measurements of naturally occurring single crystals can indicate elastic stiffnesses that can differ by 1/3 for c_{33} up to a factor of eight for the off-diagonal terms [3] from the values listed in Table 1. Although, some of the values in Table 1 differ significantly from measurements of naturally occurring single crystals, they are assumed to be the best representation of single crystal graphite elastic properties.

Fig. 1: Graphite lattice and bonding. The space group is $P1$, the stacking sequence is $ABAB$. The extreme anisotropy is due to the large difference in bonding type between the ab plane and the bc and ac planes. The ab plane contains strongly covalent sp^2 bonds of ~ 1020 kJ/mole bond energy, while the bc and ac planes contain weak π^* bonds of ~ 10 kJ/mole bond energy. Also note that each carbon not at a vertex of the $P1$ unit cell does not have a π^* bond.

Table 1: Elastic Constants of Single Crystal Graphite in GPa

Elastic Stiffness	Unirradiated	Irradiated	Ref.
c_{11}	1060	1060	[2]
c_{33}	36.5	36.5	[2]
c_{12}	180	180	[2]
c_{13}	15	15	[2]
c_{44}	0.246 (average of 20)	3.965 (average of four at neutron dose of 7.1×10^{18} nvt)	[5]

The shear term between basal planes, c_{44} , has the lowest stiffness and is worth particular mention because it is the most difficult to determine and it is the most sensitive to the

presence of dislocations and defects in the lattice. For example, neutron irradiation induced imperfections that pin dislocations [4] and increase c_{44} from 0.250 ± 0.033 GPa to 3.965 ± 0.212 GPa [5]. The bonding between basal sheets is so weak that shear between them has little resistance unless defects are present. Neutron induced point defects, grain boundaries, and nanometer-sized porosity (called Hohlstellen) can all act to impede dislocation motion [4]. This is important for carbon fibers that contain significant nanometer sized grains and porosity. An analysis of polycrystalline graphite elastic constants [6] concluded that the crystallite shear term c_{44} is the controlling factor to explain the effect of neutron irradiation on the polycrystalline elastic moduli. It is important to note that the graphites in the latter study had an average crystallite size of 1000-5000 Å, far larger than the crystallite size in carbon fibers. Fourdeux's [7] neutron irradiation of carbon fibers experiments resulted in the longitudinal modulus to increase by about 10 %, implying that dislocations in carbon fibers are not completely pinned by the porosity and small crystallite size. Therefore, the question remains as to which bound of c_{44} is more suitable to represent carbon fiber's elastic properties.

This paper first discusses preferred orientation descriptors in carbon, and follows with a discussion of three elastic constant models applied to sp^2 bonded anisotropic carbon fibers. We use the Tomé ellipsoidal self-consistent model [8] to predict the polycrystalline elastic properties. We apply this model into a procedure to determine polycrystalline porous fiber elastic properties starting with three measured properties; the longitudinal fiber modulus, fiber density, and single crystal elastic properties of graphite from Table 1. We fit the Tomé model prediction for longitudinal elastic modulus, corrected for porosity, to known fiber longitudinal modulus by adjusting the effective preferred orientation. Finally, a comparison is made between the elastic model predictions of fiber elastic constants and those back calculated from a composite laminate.

Description of Preferred Orientation in Carbon Fibers

Experimental determination of x-ray (002) diffraction intensity, $I(\varphi)$, for slender carbon and graphite fibers is complicated and error prone. Orienting bundles of fibers along a single axis is difficult for the extreme preferred orientation usually encountered with the fibers. Therefore, the effective $I(\varphi)$ that is measured of a fiber bundle in an x-ray machine is a convolution of the actual $I(\varphi)$ with spreading due to angular dispersion of fibers within the fiber tow. Bacon and Schalamon [9] have shown that fiber types with identical experimentally measured orientation half-widths can have measured axial Young's moduli differing by over a factor of three. Reynolds [10] described a focused x-ray technique that can measure the (002) diffraction arc from single fibers in a few hours of exposure. This technique eliminates the spreading of the true $I(\varphi)$ due to slight misorientations of fibers in a tow. The (002) distributions shown in Fig. 2 were measured using this technique. This figure shows a graph of an experimentally measured $I(\varphi)$ for a Type I (~2500 °C heat treatment temperature) carbon fiber under no load and under 0.79 GPa tension. This graph also compares intensity expressed in one parameter with a similar two-parameter approximation:

$$I(\varphi) = \sin^m \varphi \quad \text{and} \quad I(\varphi) = \sin^m \varphi^q. \quad (1a,b)$$

Fig. 2: Comparison of (1a) and (1b) with experimental (002) x-ray diffraction intensities for a single Type 1 (~2500 °C heat treatment temperature) carbon fiber. The experimental data is from [10]. Loading the fiber to 0.79 GPa increases the preferred orientation significantly. The results of the fits are listed in Table 3.

Table 2: (002) Diffraction Arc Approximation Fits

Unloaded Fiber (002) $I(\varphi)$ Approximation Fit Results		Loaded Fiber (002) $I(\varphi)$ Approximation Fit Results		
	One Parameter	Two Parameter	One Parameter	Two Parameter
q		0.99463		0.99503
m	26.1551	20.10889	37.01956	27.71807
χ^2	0.00127	0.00036	0.00142	0.00035

The effect of loading is to increase the degree of preferred orientation. The one-parameter fit has three times the error in χ^2 (sum of the squares of the deviations) compared to the two-parameter fit for both of the experimental measurements. Isotropy is achieved by setting $m = 0$. Increasing m is indicative of increasing preferred orientation and hence anisotropy.

Polycrystalline Elastic Constant Models

Three models are discussed to predict the elastic constants of polycrystalline materials based upon preferred orientation of the crystallites. These models are: the Voigt uniform stress, Reuss uniform strain, and Tomé ellipsoidal self-consistent models.

An inherent limitation of two of these models, the Voigt uniform strain model and the Reuss uniform stress model, is that they ignore the complex interactions at the crystallite boundaries necessary to accommodate the strain and stress jump conditions [3]. The uniform stress model assumes that the stress is constant among the crystallites and provides the upper limit of polycrystalline elastic constants. The uniform strain model assumes that the strain is constant among the crystallites, and is therefore provides the lower bound of polycrystalline elastic constants. The differences between these two models increase with increasing crystallite anisotropy and decreasing preferred orientation for most crystals.

The self-consistent model considers the case of an elastic inclusion embedded in a homogeneous equivalent medium (HEM) with the same elastic properties as those of the polycrystal [11, 12]. This model assumes that the bulk strain is the average of the individual crystallite strains. The advantage of the self-consistent model over the constant stress and constant strain models is that it considers the interactions of a grain with the surrounding HEM. The self-consistent model can also take into account non-equiaxed grain shapes. Graphites and carbons have crystallite grain shapes that depend strongly on deposition conditions, heat treatment temperatures, and meso-phase (intermediate phase(es) between initial hydrocarbon and final carbon phase) deformation conditions.

The ellipsoidal self-consistent model [8] solves the problem of an ellipsoidal elastic inclusion (ellipsoidal Eshelby inclusion [13]) embedded in a HEM. The self-consistency arises from numerically adjusting the elastic properties of the HEM to coincide with the average of the inclusions. This model accurately represents intergranular interactions only in very oriented polycrystalline highly anisotropic materials. The ability of this model to accurately predict elastic constants in highly oriented carbon fibers will be evaluated in the following section.

We applied the ellipsoidal self-consistent model to calculate carbon fiber elastic constants. A computer program, written by Tomé, takes an input file which describes the preferred orientation as weighting factors at a given angular window in a coordinate system as described in the Bunge notation [14]. The file orientation weights were calculated using:

$$w_{\bar{\theta}, \bar{\varphi}} = \int_{\varphi_j}^{\varphi_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} I(\theta) \sin \theta \, d\theta \, d\varphi \quad , \quad (2)$$

where

$$\theta_i = i\delta\theta \quad , \quad \varphi_j = j\delta\varphi \quad , \quad \omega = 0 \quad , \quad (3)$$

$I(\theta)$ is given by equation (1b), θ , φ , ω are the Bunge angles, δ is angular window width, and i , j are the angular window steps. Typical analyses were performed using 1368 equivalent grains to represent the distribution of preferred orientation. The Tomé program also calculates elastic constants using the uniform stress and uniform strain models, hence the two-parameter approximation, (1b), can be conveniently employed. Model predictions differed by about 10 % when the two parameter approximation (1b) for $I(\theta)$ was used instead of the one parameter approximation (1a) for the cases shown in Fig. 2.

Carbons consisting of sp^2 bonding can exhibit extremely anisotropic elastic and thermal expansion properties, and are hence excellent example materials to develop a practical analytical procedure to predict their elastic constants. Furthermore, significant porosity exists in these materials due to packing effects caused by the small crystallite size of carbons and graphites combined with the typically large crystallite aspect ratios. The porosity consists of nanometer-sized voids. These voids can also become highly ellipsoidal in carbon fibers exhibiting a large degree of preferred orientation.

APPLICATION OF ELASTIC CONSTANT MODELS TO ORIENTED SP^2 BONDED CARBON FIBERS

Carbon fibers have significant porosity on the order of 20 %. This porosity has a very large aspect ratio along the fiber axis [7]. The effect of porosity is accounted for by the application of the Halpin-Tsai equations [1]. Based on an analysis of x-ray circular intensity measurements [7], the porosity aspect ratio is 100,000. The rule of mixtures is applied to correct the Poisson's ratios for the effect of porosity.

Table 3: Elastic Model Calculations of Carbon Fibers

Case:	Type I Fiber, No stress, Irradiated Properties	Type I Fiber, No stress, Irradiated Properties	Type I Fiber, No stress, Non- Irradiated Properties	Type II Fiber, IM- 6, Irradiated Properties	Type II Fiber, IM- 6, Non- Irradiated Properties	Type II Fiber, IM- 6, Non- Irradiated Properties	
M	20.10889 (see Table 2)	4.5 (fitted)	7.15 (fitted)	3.35 (fitted)	4.85 (fitted)	3.6 (fitted)	
Crystallite Lengths	1	0.14	0.14	0.25	0.25	0.14	
	2	0.14	0.14	0.25	0.25	0.14	
	3	0.86	0.86	0.86	0.75	0.86	
Upper Bound (Voigt):	E_{11} ,	700.65	601.96	646.14	542.87	607.60	577.84
	E_{33} ,	292.09	308.70	292.57	317.46	302.50	311.24
	$G_{12}=$	171.72	178.16	175.65	178.09	176.68	176.83
	G_{13} ,						
	Gpa						
	G_{23} ,	105.82	120.92	112.63	125.48	117.85	122.40
	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
ν_{31}	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.10	
ν_{32}	0.24	0.21	0.22	0.20	0.21	0.20	
Experiment:	E_{11} ,	355, [10]	355, [10]	355, [10]	276	276	276
	$G_{12}= G_{13}$, GPa	24.8, [10]	24.8, [10]	24.8, [10]			
	E_{11} , GPa	531.16	354.27	354.74	276.83	275.47	277.41
	$E_{22}=E_{33}$, GPa	37.50	48.46	25.13	55.93	32.33	30.93
	$G_{12}= G_{13}$, GPa	56.77	55.80	40.11	54.26	39.81	38.12
Self- Consisten	G_{23} ,	12.08	17.58	8.19	20.68	11.03	10.55
	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.34	0.38	0.46	0.35	0.42	0.44
	ν_{31}	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.07	0.05	0.05
	ν_{32}	0.37	0.28	0.41	0.26	0.35	0.35
Lower Bound (Reuss):	E_{11} ,	75.23	31.86	2.64	27.00	2.19	1.95
	E_{33} ,	17.91	16.87	1.29	16.94	1.27	1.26
	$G_{12}=$	6.36	7.15	0.45	7.25	0.47	0.48
	G_{13} ,						
	GPa						
	G_{23} ,	5.32	5.58	0.37	5.68	0.37	0.38
	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.33	0.33	0.38	0.32	0.38	0.38
ν_{31}	0.08	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.23	0.26	
ν_{32}	0.47	0.39	0.56	0.37	0.53	0.50	

Comparison of the calculated elastic constants with literature reported and measured experimental data requires conversion of the elastic constants to engineering Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios. The models calculate elastic constants with the 3 axis along the fiber

axis, and the 2 and 1 axes normal to the fiber axis, thereby maintaining hexagonal symmetry. Common engineering design practice is to consider the fiber axis to be along the 1 axis, called *special orthotropic symmetry*. Therefore a coordinate transformation is performed on the calculated elastic constants notation via the fourth order tensor transformation rule [15].

Table 3 compares the three models for two different carbon fibers, a Type I fiber (~2500 °C HTT) whose experimental (002) diffraction arc is shown in Fig 2, and a Type II fiber (Hercules IM-6 ~1600 °C HTT). The reported moduli and Poisson's ratios are corrected for porosity as described above and are listed using specially orthotropic symmetry. The ellipsoidal crystallite lengths are reported using hexagonal symmetry notation with the 3 axis along the fiber axis. The lengths are dimensionless and only the ratios of the lengths are important. The values used are qualitatively obtained from high-resolution transmission micrographs [7, 16]. The value of q used in (1b) is held constant at 0.99463 for all of the cases. The density used for the Type I fiber is that reported for the Type II fiber ($\rho = 1.76 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and should be considered conservatively low; the actual density may be 5-8 % higher. Note that none of the models accurately predict the experimentally measured axial modulus for the Type I fiber when the experimental (002) diffraction arc is used. m from (1b) is adjusted in the second and third columns such that the self-consistent model Young's modulus along the fiber, E_{11} , fits the experimental measurement. However, the shear modulus, G_{12} , predicted by the self-consistent model does not closely correspond to Reynolds's experimental measurement, even for the non-irradiated single crystal property case. Columns four through six compare the results when m is fitted so that the self-consistent model prediction for E_{11} matches the experimental fiber axial moduli for Hercules IM6 fiber. Column four uses the irradiated single crystal higher value for c_{44} , while column five shows the results when the non-irradiated lower value is used. The non-fitted parameters differ by up to 50 % between the two cases of c_{44} . Column six uses the same single crystal properties as five, but with a larger crystallite aspect ratio. The lower bound and upper bound cases are listed to illustrate the difference between their predictions and experimental measurements of carbon fiber elastic constants. This is attributed to the high, but far from perfect, degree of preferred orientation common in carbon fibers. The magnitude of the difference between the upper and lower bound model values also illustrate the severity of the problem of estimating elastic constants of polycrystals consisting of highly anisotropic crystallites. There is also a tremendous difference between the upper and lower bound model values and the experimentally measured moduli. This second difference is in contrast to what has been previously determined for less anisotropic bulk carbons where the porosity corrected, lower bound model (constant stress) predicted moduli were very close to experimental measurements [3].

Effect of c-Axis Spacing on the Elastic Models Predictions

Polycrystalline graphite and carbon fibers have an interlayer c axis spacing as determined from the x-ray analysis that is greater than the single crystal value shown in Table 1. The c -axis spacing in polycrystalline graphite is a strong function of maximum heat treatment temperature and a weak function of maximum heat treatment time [17]. For example, Type 1 carbon fibers have a c axis spacing of about 3.39 Å [18]. The increase in c -axis spacing effects the crystallite density and elastic stiffnesses c_{33} , and possibly c_{13} and c_{44} . This results in a unit cell volume expansion of about 1.3 % and hence a theoretical density of 2230 kg/m³. Since actual fiber densities are considerably smaller, due to the presence of nano-porosity, small changes in the c -axis spacing have a negligible effect on the macroscopic density. Decreasing c_{33} by 25 % of the value in Table 1 had no significant effect on the three elastic

models' results for the case of a sine approximation with $m = 10$, $q = 0.994$. This and the results shown in Table 3 indicate that the models' predicted elastic constants are mostly dependent upon the graphite single crystal c_{11} , c_{44} , and the polycrystalline preferred orientation.

RESONANT ULTRASOUND SPECTROSCOPY OF A LAMINATED COMPOSITE

We have used Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy (RUS) to determine the elastic constants of a unidirectional laminated composite of IM6 fibers in a 3501/6 epoxy matrix ($v_f = 0.62$). RUS can determine all of the elastic constants at once to a deterministic level of accuracy, the level of which depends upon the material, quality of machining of the sample, appropriateness of the symmetry model, and identification of the fitting peaks [19]. It is especially accurate in determining the shear elastic constants and this is facilitated by the first few resonances that are usually strong and are almost entirely due to shear modes. This also has the advantage of increasing the accuracy of determining the c_{11} and c_{12} .

The application of RUS to fibrous composite systems is relatively new and poses special difficulties. RUS has recently been applied to determine the elastic constants of a ceramic-fiber laminated-ceramic matrix composite and many similarities exist in the application to polymer matrix composites [20]. There are significant differences that are important in RUS between laminated ceramic fiber ceramic matrix composites and carbon fiber laminated polymer matrix composites. These include the much lower Q (resonant gain factor) typical in polymers, a far greater anisotropy and greater differences in stiffness constants between the fiber and matrix. The lower Q factor in the polymer composite leads to broader peaks of lower intensity. The typically lower values for the shear and transverse elastic constants in the polymer composite results in many more predicted peaks. The combination of low Q and low shear and transverse elastic constants results in many lost peaks that must be correctly accounted for in the fitting process. Hence, reasonably accurate starting values of the elastic constants must be provided.

The sample dimensions were 5.70 (5.691), 5.44 (5.437), and 6.20 (6.207) mm, along the 1, 2, and 3 (fiber) axes, using the hexagonal symmetry orientation. The values in parentheses are the best-fit sample dimensions. The composite spectrum was scanned from 100 kHz to 1 MHz and 31 peaks were identified and are listed in Table 4. Fig. 3 shows an example scan. Several scans were performed with repositioning the sample between the transducers from one scan to the next in order to improve the distinction between real and false resonances due to contact artifacts. Each scan was an average of 5 or 8 individual scans to improve the signal to noise ratio. 293 peaks were estimated from the fitting program between the lowest and highest observed resonance; and the best fit assuming hexagonal (transversely isotropic) symmetry resulted in a RMS error of 0.23%. This is approximately the same overall error to what has been reported for the other laminated composite [20]. This level of error may be the lowest that can be expected from laminated fibrous composite materials, although it is typically about an order of magnitude higher than what can be achieved in polycrystalline metals. The error that could be obtained by starting with the manufacturer supplied elastic constant data shown in Table is ~2.35% RMS. Iterating around that data results in the axial c_{11} dropping to ~150 GPa, an unrealistically low value considering the ease of traditional measurement and rule of mixture prediction of that property. The lowest RMS error obtained after iterating around the manufacturer supplied data is about ~0.50% RMS.

Table 4: RUS Peaks

Spectra Peaks, kHz	Fitting Weights	Best Fit Results
136.030	30	135.846
152.086	2	152.691
217.710	20	217.535
252.950	6	254.497
293.790	10	293.356
301.001	1	301.402
309.409	1	311.942
323.023	3	323.875
336.236	2	340.088
351.452	1	350.514
363.464	1	365.025
371.472	4	368.875
395.890	3	396.287
402.300	12	403.629
426.727	2	428.055
449.149	3	450.979
483.580	4	482.347
493.990	6	492.003
536.436	2	536.182
546.246	1	546.816
558.350	1	558.335
579.170	3	578.869
660.960	1	658.940
675.670	3	674.291
761.568	2	759.548
785.280	2	780.870
804.500	3	804.060
827.020	2	828.473
853.450	5	853.184
895.790	2	895.771
945.340	6	945.118

Fig. 1: RUS spectra of a unidirectional IM6-3501/6 composite. This is a composite plot of scans performed from 100-500 kHz, 500-600 kHz, 600-700 kHz, and 700-1000 kHz. Transition artifacts occur at the boundaries between scans.

Table 5: IM6-3501/6 Unidirectional Laminate Elastic Properties

E_{11} , GPa	$E_{22}=E_{33}$, GPa	G_{23} , GPa	$G_{13}=G_{12}$, GPa	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{21}	$\nu_{23}=\nu_{32}$
170 ^(a)	9.5 ^(a)	3.45 ^(a)	5.75 ^(a)	0.31 ^(a)	0.04 ^(a)	0.34 ^(a)
172.4 ^(b)	6.41 ^(b)	5.44 ^(b)	5.69 ^(b)	0.324 ^(b)	0.011 ^(b)	0.381 ^(b)

^(a) Supplied by Hercules, Inc. ^(b) Resonant Ultrasound Spectroscopy (RUS)

Table 6: RUS Best Fit Elastic Constants, GPa In Specially Orthotropic Symmetry

c_{11}	$c_{22}=c_{33}$	$c_{12}=c_{13}$	c_{23}	c_{44}	$c_{66}=c_{55}$
174±0.16	7.57±0.079	3.62±0.01579	2.93±0.0026	2.32±0.0007	5.65±0.0045

Table 6 lists the best-fit elastic constants of the unidirectional composite in specially orthotropic orientation. The listed errors are the variation in estimated values necessary to change the value of χ^2 by 2 %. Table 5 compares the unidirectional laminate elastic properties in engineering Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios in specially orthotropic symmetry, as supplied by the manufacturer and measured by RUS.

EXPANSION OF THE HALPIN-TSAI EQUATIONS TO HANDLE ANISOTROPIC CONSTITUENTS

A most interesting comparison can be made between the elastic model predictions of fiber elastic properties and those properties predicted by the Halpin-Tsai equations. The Halpin-Tsai equations were developed using isotropic reinforcement materials, and their application to anisotropic reinforcements is questionable. Table 8 lists the 3501/6 epoxy resin and IM6 fiber engineering elastic properties. The elastic properties of the fiber in Table 7 are listed for comparison with calculated respective properties listed in Table 7. The elastic properties for the resin are used in the Halpin-Tsai equations. Only the fiber axial modulus can be directly

determined, the other listed elastic properties were back-calculated from laminate data. Table 7 lists fiber properties predicted from the Halpin-Tsai equations in column two. A comparison of these properties to the self-consistent model predictions of the IM6 fiber listed in Table 3, which are repeated in column one of Table 7, is not close. However, the following modifications can be made to the Halpin-Tsai equations that will greatly increase the correspondence between the laminate measured Halpin-Tsai back-calculated fiber properties and those predicted by the ellipsoidal self-consistent elastic model of preferred orientation, when corrected for porosity. ν_{21} of the composite and the fiber can be calculated by:

$$\nu_{21} = \nu_{12} \frac{E_{22}}{E_{11}}. \quad (4)$$

The fiber Poisson's ratios listed in column two and three of Table 7 are calculated using the rule of mixtures, as suggested by Halpin [1]. ν_{21} in columns two and three of Table 7 are calculated using (4).

The modification for the calculation of E_{22} utilizes the Sih, Paris, and Irwin effective modulus for orthotropic materials [21], which has been previously employed to correlate mode I fracture toughness with fracture energy in orthotropic materials. The effective modulus is given by:

$$E_{22}^{eff} = 2 \left[\frac{(c_{23} + c_{33})(c_{12}^2 - c_{11}c_{33})}{(c_{23} - c_{33})(-2c_{12}^2 + c_{11}(c_{23} + c_{33}))^2} \right]^{-1/2} \left[\frac{-2c_{12}^2 - 2c_{12}c_{66} + (c_{23} + c_{33}) \left(c_{11} + 2c_{66} \sqrt{\frac{c_{12}^2 - c_{11}c_{33}}{c_{23}^2 - c_{33}^2}} \right)}{c_{66}(c_{23} + c_{33})} \right]^{-1/2}. \quad (5)$$

when expressed in elastic stiffness constants for specially orthotropic orientation. The c_{ij} in

(5) are corrected for fiber porosity using the Halpin-Tsai equations for the diagonal terms and the rule-of-mixtures for the off-diagonal terms. Thus, for determining E_{22} using the Halpin-Tsai equations, the engineering elastic property of the reinforcement, p_r , becomes:

$$p_r^{E_{22}} = E_{22}^{eff} \left(\frac{E_{22}}{E_{11}} \right). \quad (6)$$

The correction factors when calculating the shear terms involve non-integer powers. p_r becomes:

$$p_r^{G_{12}} = \sqrt{G_{12}G_{23}} \quad , \quad p_r^{G_{23}} = G_{12}^{1/3}G_{23}^{2/3} \quad (7a, b)$$

for determining G_{12} and G_{23} , respectively.

A comparison between column one and column three of Table 7 reveals a close correspondence among all of the engineering elastic constants, with the exception of E_{22} , where the difference is 13.7%. These corrections are admittedly rather arbitrary due to the limited number of experimental cases (present and isotropic), but (6)-(7a, b) have the advantage that in the limit of isotropy they simplify back to E and G , respectively.

Table 7: Comparison of Elastic Model Predicted Fiber Properties and Halpin-Tsai Predicted Fiber Properties

Property	Self-Consistent (Table 3, case 4)	Halpin-Tsai Back Calculated From RUS data	Modified Halpin-Tsai Back Calculated From RUS data
E_{11} , GPa	275.47	276	276
$E_{22}=E_{33}$, GPa	32.33	8.15	37.45
$G_{13}=G_{12}$, GPa	39.81	20.97	39.88
G_{23} , GPa	11.03	17.11	11.25
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.423	0.299	0.410
ν_{21}	0.052	0.00754	0.058
$\nu_{23}=\nu_{32}$	0.352	0.391	0.350

Table 8: Composite Constituent Properties

Property	IM6 Fiber	3501/6 Epoxy
E_{11} , GPa	276 ^(a)	4.24 ^(a) , 4.275 ^(b)
E_{22} , GPa	13.8 ^(a)	
G_{12} , GPa	108 ^(a)	1.793 ^(b)
ν_{12}	0.28 ^(a)	0.365 ^(a) , 0.34 ^(b)
ν_{23}	0.30 ^(a)	
ρ , g/cm ³	1.76 ^(a)	1.265

^(a) Supplied by Hercules, Inc.
^(b) Courtesy of Don Adams, University of Wyoming.

SUMMARY

The ellipsoidal self-consistent model provides much more accurate predictions of elastic constants of highly oriented carbon fibers than either the constant stress or constant strain models. However, model predictions when experimental (002) diffraction arcs are used significantly overestimate the axial fiber moduli. The correspondence improves considerably when corrections are made for porosity and m is adjusted such that the ellipsoidal self-consistent model prediction for E_{11} matches the experimentally measured axial modulus. The essential effect of adjusting m in such a fashion is to provide a correction for the complex stress and strain accommodations occurring at the graphite crystallite grain boundaries that differ from the mathematically ideal accommodations implicit in the ellipsoidal self-consistent model. The porosity correction is made using the Halpin-Tsai equations to account

for the long axial aspect ratios of fiber porosity reported by TEM investigations [7, 9]. An advantage of choosing the fiber density and axial modulus as inputs is that they are easily measured accurately and are usually supplied by the fiber manufacturer.

Significant differences occur in model predictions, which depend upon the chosen single crystal value of c_{44} . The ellipsoidal self-consistent model predictions based upon the irradiated (pinned glissile dislocations) single crystal c_{44} value overestimates the fiber transverse and shear elastic properties by a significant factor. Use of the non-irradiated single crystal c_{44} value yields much more realistic fiber elastic properties. This result addresses the question of the role of the small crystallite size and porosity in Type II fibers. Grain boundaries and spherical porosity (Hohlstellen) have been observed in the TEM to impede the motion of glissile dislocations in graphite [4]. The elastic model predictions indicate that grain boundaries and porosity in carbon fibers do not significantly impede the motion of glissile dislocations.

Significant differences exist between the Halpin-Tsai equations back calculated fiber properties from RUS measured unidirectional composite laminate properties and the predicted properties based upon the Tomé ellipsoidal self-consistent model. These differences are attributed to the fact that the Halpin-Tsai equations were developed using isotropic reinforcement materials and hence are not directly applicable to cases of anisotropic reinforcement materials. Simple correction factors are proposed that greatly improve the correspondence between the self-consistent model predictions and the RUS back calculated fiber properties. These correction factors simplify back to the original Halpin-Tsai equations in the limit of isotropic reinforcement materials.

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